

Influence of WhatsApp on Performance in Coordinate Geometry among Students of the Federal College of Education Zaria, Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study aimed at investigating the influence of WhatsApp on NCE 1 students' academic performance in Coordinate Geometry in Federal College of Education Zaria. Quasi experimental involving pretest and posttest research design was used for the study. The targeted population of the study was 366 NCE 1 students registered for the 2019/2020 academic session in the Department of Mathematics. The sample of the study was 140 students selected through Multistage and Stratified Sampling. The sample comprised 61 students (29 male and 32 female) students were assigned to the experimental group and 79 (42 male and 37 female) students to the control group. The average age of students was 19 years. The study was guided by two research questions and two research hypotheses. The CGPT was subjected to both face and content validation by two experts in the field of mathematics education. The final draft of CGPT was trial tested using 30 students that were part of the population but not part of the sample and test-retest method was used to obtain the reliability to coefficient which was found to be 0.82. A WhatsApp strategy lesson plan prepared by the researchers was used to teach the experimental group while the control group was taught using conventional method. Findings from study shows a significant difference in the mean performance score between the experimental group (mean= 72.67, SD= 11.811) and the control group (mean= 51.58, SD= 9.85), $t(138) = 11.52$, $p = 0.001$. The study also revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean performance score between male and female students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp male (mean= 71.79, SD= 12.37) and female (mean= 74.13, SD= 11.52), $t(59) = 0.762$, $p = 0.224$. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that the serving teachers be trained in current innovation teaching strategies such as WhatsApp strategy through workshops, seminars, conferences and in serve programmes.

Keywords: WhatsApp, Coordinate Geometry, Performance, Covid-19.

Introduction

Mathematics teaching and learning have become so imperative to the scientific and technological developments of any nation of the world. This is why the Federal Government of Nigeria, in its National Policy on Education (NPE, 2013), made mathematics one of the core subjects in the secondary school curriculum. It is also a pre-requisite for students to obtain credit in the subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) before gaining admission into any tertiary institution in Nigeria. This is necessary because disciplines such as the sciences, humanities, arts, etc, cannot be studied successfully without the application of mathematics. Coordinate Geometry according to Saidu (2019), is a field of study in Mathematics that bridges the gap between Algebra and Geometry. This is attested to the fact that the course content covers the following topics; Circles, Parabola, Ellipse, Hyperbola, and Equation of Lines. It is one of the core courses in Mathematics taught at National Certificate in Education (NCE) level one (1). The study of Coordinate Geometry dates back to ancient times because Isaac Newton (1642-1727) was the first to work on Functional Exponents and Coordinate Geometry to drive solutions to Algebraic Equations. As a result of this development, Scientist employs the knowledge of Coordinate Geometry in solving geometrical problems. Brown, Evans, Hunt, McIntosh, Pender, and Ramagge (2011) opined, the techniques of coordinate geometry are used in courses like Statistics, Calculus, Graph, Algebra, etc. Therefore, Coordinate Geometry is a gateway to learning other concepts in Mathematics and Science in general.

Despite the importance of Coordinate Geometry, students failed in answering questions that have to do with the concept. This was attested from WAEC (2019) Chief Examiner's report in which students failed in solving geometrical

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questions and this translates to poor performance by NCE 1 Mathematic students on coordinate geometry because students fail and score low grades in the subject. Even though many factors were responsible for the poor performance which include; teaching method been used by teachers of Mathematics, students lack interest, class size, lack of use of teaching aids to mention a few. However, research studies have shown that the conventional lecture method has a greater effect on poor performance by students. The method has been described by Usman (2007) as one that encourages students to learn without understanding. To attest to that, WAEC (2010) noted, lecture method of teaching doesn't meet the needs of the learners as such perform poorly in mathematics. Inah (2014) describes the conventional lecture method as it allows teachers to within a short period, cover a wide area of the syllabus without minding students' understanding. To this effect, researchers such as Ennyam and Yaratan (2018) suggested, the use of computer-aided technology in teaching and learning as an alternative strategy in teaching courses such as Coordinate Geometry.

One of such technological developments is the emergence of digital media in today's communication system of the world. Smartphones as digital media has several applications that allow for social interactions among groups and individuals. These applications include; Facebook, WhatsApp, Integra, Twitter, Snap Chats, Skype, Email, etc, are termed Social Networking Sites (SNSs) (Al-Mothana, 2017). According to Al-Mothana (2017), SNSs are often used by university students all over the world which suggests they could be used for educational purposes. Digital communication among students and their teachers is on the increase in the last decade through this SNSs (Hamiyet, 2016). Students often use these sites to obtain information through question and answer which allow for knowledge acquisition. Orij and Anikpo (2019) opined that 80% of active users of these SNSs are youths who are mainly students cut across Educational Institutions in Nigeria. They describe these SNS sites as technological platforms that allow for interactive web content formation, collaboration, and discussion by contributors.

One of these SNSs as noted by Al-Mothan (2017), is the WhatsApp application. It is a Smartphone application used as a means of sending and receiving instant messages to and from individuals and groups (Bouhnik and Deshen, 2014). The application, allows users to exchange text messages, images, videos, and audio using internet connections. Even though, WhatsApp as a new tool in education has positive characteristics as other previous technological tools used in teaching and learning. Thus, Bouhnik and Deshen (2014) noted that WhatsApp has some up-to-date features that encourage teachers and students to use it to enhance academic performance. Online collaboration, as prompted by WhatsApp instant messages help in facilitating learning, because learners can easily exchange information, have their inquiries quickly answered, construct knowledge and create class participation. It is therefore easy for mathematics teachers to create and form groups of students with WhatsApp and use it as a teaching strategy in teaching and learning concepts in the subject. Therefore, teaching and learning of mathematical concepts such as; Algebra, Trigonometry, Coordinate Geometry, Number and Numeration, etc can be taught to students using the WhatsApp platform.

The emergence of Pandemic Diseases in particular COVID-19, according to Ebohon, Obienu, Irabor, Amadin, and Omoregie (2021) was a result of a widespread of cases of patients with pneumonia admitted to Wuhan hospitals in China in late 2019. As a result of the widespread of the disease across the globe, World Health Organization (WHO) in 2019 declared, COVID-19 as a pandemic. Thus, as a result 87 percent of the world's students were affected by school closure from about 180 countries as reported by (Jacob, 2020) . Throughout the year 2020, all human activities were greatly affected by the pandemic spread across the world.

In Nigeria, Ebohon et al (2021) noted, tertiary institutions were taken unaware when the disease appeared because there was no contingency arrangement for such a problem. All activities including economic, religious, health, education, sports, transport, agriculture, mining, and many others, were seriously affected by the spread of the disease across the country. The Federal Government of Nigeria had to join in closing all schools public and private in March, 2020. The school started re-opening in October, 2020. While, students were at home due to the lockdown, the Federal and State Governments introduce Radio and Television educational programmes to make the students busy doing something. Administrators in private and tertiary institutions came up with online teaching and learning for their students. Some of the Social Media Applications, Television, and Radio, were used as an alternative method of teaching and learning for their students across the educational levels of the institutions.

The prevailing teaching methodology in teaching mathematics courses in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria has been the Conventional Lecture method. The method has become a subject of concern among stakeholders in Education because it is largely teacher-centered. Students lack of interaction and activity during teaching and learning results in a lack of understanding of what is been taught in the class. One of the courses at the NCE 1 level that gives students a lot of difficulties is Coordinate Geometry because it's considered abstract. Students find it difficult to understand its concepts mainly due to the method of

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teaching. It is for this reason that the study is designed to determine the influence of WhatsApp on NCE 1 student's performance in Coordinate Geometry.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to determine the influence of WhatsApp and NCE 1 students' performance in Coordinate Geometry in FCE Zaria. The objectives of the study are;

1. To examine the performance of students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp and those taught using the Lecture method.
2. To determine whether there is difference in the performance of male and female students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp.

Research Question

The following questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the mean difference in the performance of students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp and those taught using Lecture method?
2. What is the mean difference in performance between male and female students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant

1. There is no significant difference in performance between the students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp and those taught using the Lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference in performance between male and female student taught coordinate geometry using WhatsApp.

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test control group design. The targeted population for the study consisted of all 366 NCE 1 students registered in the Department of Mathematics for the 2019/2020 academic session. A sample of 140 students comprising of 78 males and 62 females was selected through a Multi-stage Sampling technique. In the first stage, stratified sampling technique was used by dividing the students into two strata, that is those students who have WhatsApp applications on their phones and those who don't have the application or nor phone at all. In the second stage, proportional sampling was used to select from each course combination a certain number of students having the application and also those not having the application.

Coordinate Geometry Performance Test (CGPT) was used as an instrument for the data collection. The CGPT was a 20-item multiple-choice question that required students to choose the correct answers from the options lettered A-D. The instrument CGPT was subjected to both face and content validation by two experts in the field of Mathematics Education where their comments and suggestions were used in modifying some of the test items. The final draft of CGPT was trial tested using 30 students that were not part of the sample. A test-retest method was used to determine the reliability of the CGPT and was found to be 0.82. The treatment lasted for six weeks, after which a post-test was administered to both the experimental and control groups. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while a t-test was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in mean performance scores between those students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp and those taught using Lecture Method?

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Table 1: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation of student performance taught using WhatsApp and Lecture method

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Experimental	61	26.57	4.537	72.67	11.811	46.10
Control	79	25.92	8.639	51.58	9.846	25.66
Mean Difference				21.09		

The results Table 1 show the difference in the mean between the two groups at pre-test as 0.65. At post-test, the Table revealed that the difference was 21.09 in favour of the Experimental group. The mean gains of the Experimental and Control groups were 46.10 and 25.66 respectively. This shows that the experimental group had higher mean performance scores than the control group. To test the significance of this difference independent sample t-test analysis was used.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in performance between those students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp and those taught using Lecture Method.

Table 2: Summary of t-test Analysis on Students Performance between Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	t-value	P-value
Experimental	61	72.67	11.811	138	11.52	0.001
Control	79	51.58	9.846			

Table 2 revealed that there was significant difference between the mean performance scores of experimental (mean = 72.67) and the control group (mean = 51.58) at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance $t(138) = 11.52, p = 0.0001$. Therefore, hypothesis one was rejected. This implies that, the mean difference in the performance scores between the students in the Experimental group and Control group was significant. The students taught using WhatsApp performed significantly better than those students taught using the conventional method

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in the mean performance scores between Male and Female Students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation between male and female students in the Experimental Group

Gender	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Male	29	27.69	5.100	71.79	12.370	44.10
Female	32	25.19	6.162	74.13	11.519	48.94
Mean Difference				2.34		

Table 3 shows the difference in the mean between gender at pre-test as 2.50 in favour of male students while at post-test, the female had a mean score of 74.13 and the male had a mean score of 71.79 showing a difference of 2.34 in favour of the female students. The mean gain of the male was 44.10 while that of female students was 48.94.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in performance between male and female students taught coordinate geometry using WhatsApp.

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Table 4: Summary of t- test Analysis on Performance between Male and Female Students

Gender	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t-value	p-value
Male	29	71.79	12.370	59	0.7624	0.2244
Female	32	74.13	11.519			

Table 4 above shows $t(59) = 0.7624$ and $p = 0.224$, with $p > 0.05$, the null hypothesis was retained. This result implies that, the mean difference between male and female students who were taught using WhatsApp was not significant. It means that, the male and female students equally benefitted from the WhatsApp teaching strategy.

Discussion of Findings

The result in Table 2 showed that, significant difference existed between those students taught Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp and those exposed to Coordinate Geometry using the Lecture method. Therefore, the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance was rejected. This is in line with the study of Saidu (2019) which showed that students taught coordinate geometry using GeoGebra teaching strategy perform better than those taught using the lecture method of teaching.

In the test of hypothesis 2 in Table 4 revealed that, there is no significant difference between male and female students taught Coordinate Geometry with WhatsApp. This finding is in agreement with the study of Molina, Gercia, and Mortoro (2010) who did not find a significant difference between the performance of male and female student Web-Based learning and practice. The researchers conclude that WhatsApp is gender-friendly.

Conclusion

The findings of this study provide empirical support that, the teaching of Coordinate Geometry using WhatsApp improved students' performance much more than the lecture method. It is important to note that, the performance of students in Coordinate Geometry could be significantly improved if Mathematics Educators could explore the use of social media such as WhatsApp, Tweeter, Facebook, etc and appropriately utilized them in the teaching and learning of Mathematics courses. The study empirically shows that, social media is capable of helping students to understand Coordinate Geometry concepts better and could bridge the gender gap in terms of student's performance. In addition to that, study revealed that It is also important to note that, social media could serve as an alternative teaching strategy in situations like the emergence of Pandemic in our schools, right from primary to tertiary Institutions in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. NCE students should be exposed to the new teaching strategy (WhatsApp) in teaching and learning in all courses offered by FCE Zaria.
2. curriculum writers should develop curriculum that allows for using WhatsApp as a teaching strategy in our Educational Institutions.
3. Conferences/ Workshops should be organized by organizations such as MAN to enlighten the teaching staff on the new teaching strategy.

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